

Flux/Flow and Probabilistic Considerations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 10, 2022

In previous notes (1) we discussed two flux/flow equations $\frac{dA(x,t)}{dx} = p$ and $\frac{dA}{dt} = -E$ with a solution $A(x,t) = -Et + px$ which is the relativistic free particle Lagrangian $-\text{mosqrt}(1-vv)$ ($c=1$). We argued that one may convert these into two probabilistic eigenvalue equations representing free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic) quantum mechanics: $-\frac{d}{dx} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $\frac{d}{dt} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$.

In this note we try to explore the relationship to probability more closely. In particular, we try to show that for a quantum bound state the main statistical principle is not maximization of entropy, but rather local conservation of energy i.e. a constant E_n at each x which is a consequence of special relativity (even in the nonrelativistic case). In other words an E_n (average energy) must be defined in order that a 4-vector $(0, E_n)$ have meaning at each x .

Flow/Flux and Eigenvalue Equation

The two free particle flow/flux equations $\frac{dA(x,t)}{dx} = p$ and $\frac{dA}{dt} = -E$ have a solution $A = -Et + px$ (the relativistic Lagrangian $-\text{mosqrt}(1-vv)$) which is a Lorentz invariant. We argued in (1) that these may be written as eigenvalue equations with the eigenfunction being related to probability i.e.

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d}{dt} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((1b))$$

$\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is based on a Lorentz invariant, but is a curious object if considered as a probability. One may notice that $\exp(-iA)\exp(iA) = 1$ which is proportional to $P(x)$ for a free particle. The periodicity and negative values form e.g. $\cos(px)$ together with the overall imaginary number result, however, seem to be unusual. We wish to examine these in connection with the example of a particle in a box with infinite walls.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

In classical physics one considers a free particle at each x and t point. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls one limits space to $[0, L]$. A probabilistic view, however, considers all space from $-\infty$ to ∞ with probability outside $[0, L]$ being 0 and the probability within $P(x=0) = P(x=L) = 0$. Inside the box the particle is like a free particle it seems except for the fact that with time "removed" one has both forward and backward motion. Classically one would still have $P(x) = \text{constant}$.

At first these ideas seem to be inconsistent with the free particle $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ probability related function. The particle in a box picture is a stationary one with forward and backward free particle motion included. $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ suggests that two dimensions are needed to describe motion in one direction, but using $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ one may create a periodic function which may be 0 at both $x=0$ and $x=L$. In this case $p = \text{pave}$ i.e. an average momentum because the entire range of p values is needed to allow for interference to create $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p$

$a(p)\exp(ipx) = 0$ outside of $[0,L]$. These create “p average” i.e. $\sqrt{2m KEave}$ within the box. Furthermore given that one has “free particle” type motion within the box, one would expect both p and $Eave$ to be defined at each x i.e. a four-vector. Thus:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)(-pp/2m) \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)] = KE \ ave(x) = Eave \ ((2))$$

Here $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) = W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{an average of } \exp(ipx) \text{ 's.}$

Thus the idea of special relativity is still at work in this nonrelativistic example.

Nonlocality of Density

Probabilities are usually associated with pre-existing conditions. For example, a coin may yield heads or tails, a die the numbers 1 to 6 etc. For the box, the pre-existing condition is the set of “dx” boxes along x . For a free particle the probability is 1 (constant) for each box), but the periodic solution $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that two dimensions are needed to describe motion in one direction. For an average of forward and backward motion i.e $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ (equal weights) one has $2\cos(px)$ and so the probability associated with each x differs. $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ is not yet $P(x)$, but it represents much of the physical nature of $P(x)$.

This immediately suggests both a spatial and energy density at each x point, but overall $Eave$ is still a constant at each x in order that a 4-vector be defined at each x . In (2) we showed that if one considers conditional probabilities $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ then $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p) = P(p)$.

Notion of Maximization of Entropy

In classical physics one often applies the idea of maximization of entropy to a statistical problem subject to a constraint. For example, an ideal gas has N particles and a total energy and one wishes to consider how many (x_i, p_i) (i represents the i th particle and x and p are vectors) configurations one may have (involving the N particles) consistent with the total energy constraint. Each overall configuration carries the same weight and one tries to maximize the number of configurations. This is often done through probabilities. For example, if there is a probability for e of $P(e)$ then for N large, $NP(e)$ is the number of outcomes of this probability. Then the overall probability is:

$$P = \text{Product over } i \ P(e_i)^{NP(e_i)} \quad \text{Writing } P(e_i) = \exp(\ln(P(e_i))) \text{ yields } \exp(NP(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))) \quad ((3))$$

If $P = 1 / \text{number of configurations}$ then entropy is defined as: $-k \text{ Sum over } i \ P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$.

This result may also be obtained by considering factorial arrangements for large N .

This approach also applies to a wavefunction containing many states e.g.:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \ b_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((4))$$

The entropy (ignoring the effect of the entropy of the bound states is often given as (3):

$$S/(-k) = \sum \text{over } n \quad |b_n| \ln(|b_n|) \quad ((5))$$

The approach within the quantum bound state, however, seems to be different. (Furthermore we have argued that bound state entropy modifies ((5)).) The bound state itself is described by probabilities, $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, but these in turn create another set of probabilities $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ and it is this second set which behaves like classical probability. Thus, ((5)) becomes, with $S(n \text{ bound}) = S_x + S_p(n)$ for a particle in a well.

$$S/(-k) = \sum \text{over } n \quad |W_n(x)W_n(x) a_n(p)a_n(p) b_n| \ln \{ |W_n(x)W_n(x) a_n(p)a_n(p) b_n| \}$$

$$= \sum \text{over } n \quad |b_n| \ln\{|b_n|\} + |b_n| \{ \int dp \quad |a_n(p)a_n(p)| \ln(a_n) + \int dx \quad WW \ln(WW) \}$$

where the last terms are: $|b_n| S(n \text{ bound})$ ((6))

We have included $W_n(x)W_n(x) a_n(p)a_n(p)$ as part of the probability and describe the bound state entropy $S(n \text{ bound}) = S_x + S_p(n)$ for the particle in a box with infinite potential walls. We have previously argued such a sum allows for S to be independent of L so that adiabatic transformations involve no entropy change.

One usually sees S_x and S_p written separately (e.g. (2)) i.e. not summed (4). In quantum mechanics, it is often stated that if one knows momentum p precisely, one knows nothing about position and so the entropies S_x and S_p are kept separate. We argue that $W_n(x)W_n(x) a_n(p)a_n(p)$ should be included as a factor of $|b_n|$. For the case of a particle in a box with infinite walls, $W_n(x) = 0$ outside $[0, L]$ so one does not look for a pure momentum p in this region even though $W_n(x) = \sum \text{over } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ in this same region. Thus there seems to be a correlation between $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ and $a_n(p)a_n(p)$ and they need not be treated separately.

Quantum Bound State and No Maximization of Entropy

We have argued above that one may write $S = S_x + S_p(n)$ for a particle in a box with infinite potential. In other words a pure bound state has an entropy written in terms of Shannon's form. The purpose of $W(x) = \sum \text{over } a(p) \exp(ipx) =$ wavefunction, however, is to create the classical type probability $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ which may be used in Shannon's form for S_x . $a(p)a(p)$ is used to create $P(p)$ which may also be used in Shannon's form. The bound state, which is a statistical state, however, is driven by the rule that one wants average energy $-1/2m \int dx \quad dW_n/dx / W_n + V(x) = E_n$ at each x for reasons of special relativity i.e. one wants a 4-vector $(0, E_n)$ at each x point.

There is no maximization of entropy principle in general (although for the oscillator ground state $V(x)WW$ has the form of spatial entropy). The time-independent Schrodinger equation (i.e. the E_n constant at each x constraint) is enough to define appropriate sets of $a(p)$ for each energy level n . Thus it seems that the core of quantum mechanics, the bound state, follows a different rule than maximization of entropy.

To explore the nature of this new rule, consider the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $f(p,x) = C \exp(-(\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x))/T)$. One considers energy in terms of spatial density and the

average of Sum over p C exp(-pp/2mT). In other words the potential V(x) interacts as V(x) density(x).

In the quantum bound state, average kinetic energy at a point x is given in much the same way as in classical statistical mechanics except that one uses a(p) (not a(p)a(p)) and there is an x dependent normalization, not the constant C:

$$KE(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W(x) \quad ((7))$$

Sets of a(p) are chosen such that: $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ constant ((8))

One does not choose positions of the particle. These follow from exp(ipx) and W(x).

If one writes ((8)) as $-1/2 d/dx dW/dx = (E-V(x)) W(x)$ ((9)) one sees that the situation differs from classical statistical mechanics in which a thermal equilibrium of the same nature may be created at each x point. All that differs is that density shifts.

It seems that with a quantum bound state, one does not have the independence of altering particle positions and momenta independently due to the nature of the constraint ((8)).

Case of the Ground State Oscillator

The ground state oscillator has $W(x) = C \exp(-axx)$ and $a(p)=C2 \exp(-bpp)$ which is the same form as in classical statistical mechanics. $P(x)=WW$ and $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ retain the form. The form $a(p) = C2 \exp(-bpp)$ follows from maximization of entropy subject to an energy constraint, but using a(p) as probability i.e.

Max: $-\text{Sum over p } a(p)\ln(a(p)) + b \text{ Sum over p } a(p) pp/2m$ leads to $a(p) = C2 \exp(-b/2m pp)$

One may note that in this calculation, $\text{Sum over p } a(p) pp/2m$ is the unnormalized average energy which must be equal to $(E-V(x))W(x)$ where $V(x)=.5kxx$. Thus in this one case, the maximum entropy form $\exp(-b/2m pp)$ also satisfies ((8)) the constraint equation. Otherwise the solution of the constraint equation ((8)) with no attention paid to entropy or its maximization yields W(x).

Using $Pn(p)Pn(x)$ multiplied by $b_n b_n$, however, establishes independence of p and x just as in the classical scenario and so one may use $S = \text{Sum over n } |Pn(p)Pn(x) b_n b_n| \ln\{|Pn(p)Pn(x) b_n b_n|\}$ to describe thermodynamical properties of the $W(x)=\text{Sum over n } b_n \exp(-iEnt) Wn(x)$ system. (The effects of the pure state entropy, however, are included.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics deals with probabilities at two levels $Pn(x), Pn(p)$ which is the usual classical probabilistic approach and $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which is not linked to the maximization of entropy (except for the ground state oscillator solution). The principle used to establish W(x) we argue is that average energy at each x be a constant i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation. This is necessary to have the

four-vector $(0, E_n)$ at each x for special relativistic purposes. Thus we argue that the statistical idea governing a bound quantum state is special relativity (even for the nonrelativistic problem). This leads to a solution of $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ for a bound state. If $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ we have argued in (2) that $P_n(x) = W^*(x)W_n(x)$ and $P_n(p) = a^*(p)a_n(p)$. At this point one may define an entropy for the bound state in terms of Shannon's entropy i.e. use $P_n(p)P_n(x) = \text{probability}$. This leads to $S = S_p + S_x$. Usually one sees S_p and S_x separated (4) because if one knows p then x is unknown and vice versa. We argue that there is a fixed E_n for the bound state, but they should be added to ensure no parameter appears in quantum adiabatic expansions. There also appears to be a space-momentum probability associated with a bound state. For example, for a particle in a well, $W(x)W(x) = 0$ outside of $[0, L]$ and indicates that one does not search for momentum p in such a region. Thus, although the bound state itself is not based on entropy or its maximization, but rather on local energy conservation in order to create a 4-vector at each x $(0, E_n)$, a wavefunction of mixed bound states is consistent with thermodynamics and one should bring in an appropriate probability $W_n(x)W_n(x)a_n(p)a_n(p)$ from each bound state.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/ Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Quantum Thermodynamics and the Adiabatic Theorem (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
3. Abe, S and Okuyama, S. Similarity between Quantum Mechanics and thermodynamics: Entropy, Temperature and Carnot Cycle (2009 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1012.5581.pdf>
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box